

Assessment of the level of terminological competence of physical education teachers as the basis of professional activity

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Conditions of modern interpretation of the learning process require an increasing role of the teacher and a lesson in physical culture. The normative requirements for the teacher already form a new approach to the teaching of physical culture, where the culture of communication and the level of cultural and professional competence of the teacher of physical culture occupy an important place, which, of course, is impossible without the knowledge and skillful use of gymnastic terminology.

Purpose: *identification of the level of terminological competence of teachers of physical culture, peculiarities of using terms, reasons that prevent teachers from effectively using gymnastic terminology during their professional activities.*

Material & Methods: *in the study participated teachers of physical culture (n=87).*

Results: *certain features of the use of gymnastic terminology by teachers of physical culture are examined. They found they lacked a level of terminological competence during their professional activities when using physical exercises. The reasons not allowing teachers of physical training to effectively use gymnastic terminology are revealed.*

Conclusions: *level of terminological competence of each specialist is individual and very often requires its increase. It is established that despite the important role of using gymnastic terminology, its component in the lesson of physical culture decreases every year. A number of reasons have been identified that affect the level of terminological competence of teachers and are reflected in the quality of professional activity in general.*

Keywords: *gymnastic terminology, teacher, physical culture, terminological competence, professional activity.*

Introduction

Physical culture has absorbed the centuries-old experience of preparing a person for life, where the determining and guiding role is assigned to the teacher, trainer. Their professionalism largely determines the quality of professional activities, which in turn requires a high level of knowledge and effective practical use of acquired skills [2; 15; 20]. An important and integral component of the educational process in the conduct of sports activities is the use of gymnastic terminology. Specificity of terminology is that it briefly, accurately and affordably defines an unlimited number of physical exercises, the vast majority of which is of an abstract and artificial nature [1; 22]. Therefore, it is very difficult to explain them. To help come the notation - terms that make it possible to define exercises in one or more words [16; 23]. Knowledge and use of terms facilitates communication between teachers and students during classes, helps to simplify the description of exercises, shortens the time for explaining program material, increases interest in studies, carries a learning and developing function, and, therefore, activates and improves the learning process itself [16; 22]. But the observations of recent years have revealed a tendency to reduce the importance of gymnastic terminology when conducting physical education lessons at school [14]. Also, the analysis of the latest research and publications revealed the existing problems associated with the inadequacy of the use of terminology and the low level of possession by teachers of physical culture [9–11]. So, N. M. Kovalchuk and V. I. Sanyuka note that school teachers

do not use gymnastic terminology at lessons and do not require it from pupils. Specialists emphasize that often teachers use absolutely ungermatic, or incorrect terms [12], which leads to a lack of knowledge of the gymnastic terminology of students [10]. The authors emphasize that the quality teaching of physical culture is an important task of state significance, the implementation of which depends to a large extent on the level of professional competence of teachers and requires each specialist not only to teach program material, but also to profound knowledge and skillful use of gymnastic terminology, as the share of the educational process and a weighty component of the professional readiness of the teacher of physical education [9–11].

Nadezhda Kovalchuk and Tetyana Gnitetsky in their writings repeatedly draw attention to the mistakes of teachers that occur in the published plan-outline of the lesson and suggest ways to eliminate the shortcomings [13]. Also, the authors point to an insufficient level of knowledge among future teachers studying in universities and note that an important direction of solving this problem is the professional and competent use of gymnastic terminology by teachers in the process of professional training of future teachers of physical culture [24; 27]. L. P. Sushchenko and G. V. Olifer assert that the level of professional training of future teachers of physical culture depends on pedagogically correct communication [20; 24]. The authors note that the main factor that does not allow future teachers to effectively use gymnastic terminology is inad-

equate teaching at the place of study, ineffective control of knowledge, calls for the creation of modern perfect teaching and methodological works on the issues of gymnastic terminology [20; 24; 27].

Actual aspects of professional training of future specialists in their publications have been studied by various authors:

- possibility of professional communication in the preparation of athletes with the study of terminology in classes in the Ukrainian language (in the professional field) [25];
- efficiency of teaching vocational vocabulary in sports schools [26];
- need to create conditions for rethinking the approaches to vocational training and improving the professional activity of teachers through the modernization of the educational and pedagogical process, changing the structure of its organization in accordance with modern requirements [3, 21; 24].
- ways of formation of professional skills of teachers of physical culture [28].

Thus, the analysis of the literature made it possible to assert that the problem of the teacher's professional training is considered quite widely, but the question of professional and terminological competence of the teacher of physical culture was not yet the subject of a comprehensive scientific study, and was only partially considered in some aspects. And the authors do not touch at all the reasons that led to the existing position of terminological competence of teachers directly at the time of work in the school, to a considerable extent multiplies the relevance and social significance of our research.

Purpose of the research: identification of the level of terminological competence of teachers of physical culture, peculiarities of using terms, reasons that prevent teachers from effectively using gymnastic terminology during professional activities.

Relationship of research with scientific programs, plans, themes. Research was carried out in accordance with the thematic plan of the research work of the Kharkiv State Academy of Physical Culture for 2016–2018, the Initiative Scientific Theme of the Department of Dance Sports, Fitness and Gymnastics: "Theoretical and Methodological Basis for the Development of System-Forming Components of Physical Culture (Sports, Physical Recreation, fitness)" (2017–2020).

Material and Methods of the research

87 teachers of physical culture (49 women and 38 men), teachers of schools of the city of Kharkiv took part in the study. Of them, teachers of the highest category – 21; the first category – 24; the second category – 28; specialists (without a category) – 14. All participants have a higher special education. The age of respondents is from 22 to 67 years. Work experience – from 1,5 to 43 years. By sport specialization – representatives of sports games, martial arts, boxing, tourism, cycling, swimming, track and field athletics, sports and rhythmic gymnastics, acrobatics, etc. The consent for participation in the study was filled by the teachers of the questionnaire.

In the 2016–2017 school year, pedagogical observations, interviews, interviews and questionnaires of physical education teachers were conducted during the course of pedagogical practice by KSAPC students in Kharkiv general education schools, open lessons, thematic seminars, refresher courses and other events in relation to the significance and characteristics their use of gymnastic terminology in the course of their professional activities. The questionnaire included obtaining information through written responses to 9 standardized questions. The questionnaire was anonymous and consisted of direct questions for obtaining direct information from the respondent (Table). For each question, there were 2–5 answers. Questionnaire No. 5, 6, 9 had several options for answers, and also allowed teachers to express an individual opinion (Table).

The questionnaire consisted of three parts: introductory, main and demographic. The introductory part of the questionnaire indicated: the scientific institution where the study is being conducted; purpose and objectives of the study; the role of each respondent in solving the tasks; rules for completing the form, guarantee of confidentiality. The main part consisted of questions, the answers to which the research tasks should solve. The demographic part of the questionnaire consisted of questions that determined the characteristics of the respondent: gender, age, sport, sports qualification, place of study, work experience in school, category. These data were needed for a better analysis of the collected material. To establish contact with the respondent, this part was posted at the beginning of the questionnaire. At the end of the questionnaire, the respondent was thanked for the cooperation.

Pedagogical observations were conducted directly during the lessons of physical culture and were aimed at identifying the quality and special features of using gymnastic terminology. The purpose of the interview and the talk of determining the reasons that do not allow teachers to effectively use gymnastic terminology during their professional activities. The interview allowed getting information through oral answers of respondents to a question about the topic under study. The conversation, thanks to bilateral discussions, helped to obtain more detailed answers to questions about the reasons that prevent teachers from using gymnastics vocabulary effectively.

In the group non-simultaneous survey, 87 teachers took part. The total number of responses of the entire group of respondents to each question of the questionnaire was considered which allowed finding the percentage and using the analysis of quantitative data to identify trends in the questions studied and make their characteristics.

Results of the research and their discussion

Results of determining the specifics of using gymnastic terminology by teachers and assessing their level of terminological competence are presented in the table.

According to the results of the questionnaire it was revealed that 98,2% of teachers (85 respondents) have a common opinion that the knowledge of gymnastic terminology is necessary in their professional activities. But, in practice, it is used by 87,4% of teachers (76 respondents). At the same time, 93,1% of teachers say that this makes it possible to strengthen the quality of the teaching process of any modules, namely, it contributes to better memorization of exercises, more effec-

Determination of the level of terminological competence of teachers of comprehensive schools in Kharkiv (based on the results of the survey), n=87

No. i/o	Questions of the questionnaire	Results	
		m	%
1	Do you think that the knowledge of gymnastic terminology is necessary in the professional work of the teacher?		
a	Yes	85	98,2
b	No	2	1,8
2	When conducting physical education lessons, do you apply gymnastics vocabulary?		
a	Yes	76	87,4
b	No	0	0
c	Partially	11	12,6
3	Do you think that the use of gymnastic terminology contributes to the quality of physical education lessons?		
a	Yes	81	93,1
b	No	6	6,9
4	How do you assess your level of gymnastic terminology?		
a	High	7	8,1
b	Sufficient	50	57,4
c	Low	21	24,2
d	I can not answer	9	10,3
5	In your opinion, the use of gymnastic terminology affects (several answers were noted):		
a	Quality of training (mastering the technique of performing exercises, implementing the tasks of the lesson or training, etc.)	80	92,0
b	Facilitating communication between the trainer, teacher and student	19	21,8
c	Facilitating the explanation of exercises	77	88,5
d	Increase of motivation for studies	30	34,5
e	Your option	6	6,9
6	What difficulties do you have when using gymnastic terminology when conducting physical education lessons (several answers were noted)?		
a	I can not clearly and briefly explain the motor task (I use verbosity)	31	35,6
b	I do not know the terminological names of the exercises, the starting points	9	10,3
c	I'm confused in the teams	7	8,4
d	I can not compile and write a summary of the physical culture lesson	35	40,2
e	Your option	5	5,7
7	Do you think that you need to improve your level of terminology competence?		
a	Yes	78	89,7
b	No	4	4,6
c	I do not know	5	5,7
8	Do you think that students need to know the basics of gymnastic terminology and this is an important factor in the conduct of the educational process?		
a	Yes	71	81,6
b	No	8	9,2
c	I do not know	8	9,2
9	If you think that you need to improve your level of terminology competence, then at the expense of (several answers were noted):		
a	study of special methodical literature	67	77,0
b	holding special methodical sessions, seminars, round tables, conferences, debates	45	51,7
c	Your option	13	15,0

Remark. n – total number of teachers; m - number of answers to the questions of the questionnaire by teachers.

tive instruction in the technique of their implementation, discipline in class. It is alarming that 9,2% of teachers believe that the knowledge of gymnastic terminology is not necessarily in their professional work, and 12,6% of teachers use gymnastic terminology in part in the teaching process. It is interesting that there is a dissenting opinion among 13 teachers (15%) of 87 respondents who believe that the use of gymnastic terminology in conducting physical education lessons is not necessary and a sufficiently experienced teacher can qualitatively conduct professional activities practically without the use of terms, with the exception of several commands and titles exercises or elements by sport. The study found that 6,9% of

teachers believe that the use of gymnastic terminology does not contribute to the quality of physical education lessons. Teachers argue that instead of terminological commands and necessary explanations they use a whistle, makes it easier to conduct a lesson, promotes discipline and minimizes the use of gymnastic terminology. Teachers note that they most often use the whistle when conducting lessons, when two classes are engaged simultaneously in the hall and it is very difficult to give commands in this situation in this situation. Over time, the constant use of the whistle becomes a habit, and the significance of terminology decreases.

The analysis of the questionnaire revealed that 50 teachers (57,4%) state that the level of terminological competence in them is sufficient for the qualitative conduct of physical education lessons. But observations in physical education lessons did not confirm this: the actual level is much lower. The study showed that only 8,1% of teachers consider their level of mastery of gymnastic terminology high; 24,2% define their level as low; 10,3% of teachers could not determine their level. But all the respondents acknowledged the need to improve it by conducting special methodological sessions, seminars, round tables, conferences, debates, studying scientific and methodological literature. In the opinion of only 13 teachers out of 87 respondents, in order to effectively improve their level of terminological competence, it is necessary to regularly monitor the knowledge of terminology after carrying out the above-mentioned activities.

All respondents note that it is very difficult to master gymnastic terminology perfectly. Analysis of the survey and the results of the table shows that most problems arise when explaining the starting positions; not all teachers correctly submit commands; admit mistakes in explaining gymnastic combinations; do not always know how to disassemble and correctly communicate to the students program exercises in sports; make a lot of mistakes in the notes of lessons when writing general development and program exercises used in training modules. In this case, the main mistakes in terminology are most often noted such as verbosity and inaccuracies in explanation, distortion and confusion of terms, negatively affects the quality of the lesson [14].

On the question of the questionnaire about the possession of pupils in gymnastic terminology, 71 teachers (81,6%) answered that the students need to know the basics of gymnastic terminology and this is an important factor in the conduct of the educational process. Survey of teachers and observation of physical culture lessons revealed a positive trend in the practice of involving students in self-assembly and conducting complexes of general developmental exercises for evaluation precisely using gymnastic terminology, involving students in competitions for the best conduct of various complexes of GDE (with or without objects for the development of physical qualities and others) [4; 5]. The majority of the teachers surveyed noted that independent gymnastic exercises contribute to increasing students' self-esteem, improves their motivation for physical education lessons, introduces the element of competition, develops teamwork skills and is a means of encouraging children to learn physical culture. It is interesting to note that attendance of such lessons, where students can independently carry out exercises and encouraged for this good grades, significantly increased [5; 6; 14].

But, despite the important role of using terminology in the lessons of physical culture, its component in the lesson decreases every year. This, in the first place, is due to the fact that less and less in the schools of the city of Kharkov in the lessons of physical culture applies the module of gymnastics. Namely, he traditionally forced teachers to use more gymnastic terminology in the classroom. This trend spread with the introduction in 2009 of a modular system that enabled the teacher to plan modules for the school year independently [14; 17; 19], and in connection with the complexity and trauma of this module, teachers are not interested in including it in the plans for classes. This led to the fact that at present in many schools in the city of Kharkov the gymnastics module is not planned at all, and as a result,

the quality of using gymnastic terminology in physical education classes has received less attention and its educational and methodological has significantly decreased. The survey of teachers revealed a number of other reasons that affect the level and quality of using gymnastic terminology in physical education classes. Most teachers note that an important reason is that during the training in sporting terminology, little attention is paid to the sports terminology, and further, when the young specialist starts to work in the specialty, there is not always a competent employee who can correctly correct mistakes and professionally help him in improving terminological literacy. Also among the reasons for the teacher called family circumstances, a long break, which prevents them from working on their specialization immediately after graduation. Also, a significant reason for the teacher is the lack of control over the quality of terminology use during the educational process: on the one hand, from the school administration, and on the other, the pupils do not require the terminological competence and the quality of its use from the teacher. A significant number of teachers emphasize that in their school the administration refers to physical culture lessons as a not very important activity, and the professional level of physical education lessons is not controlled. At the same time, the most attention is paid to the design of various documents, it takes a lot of time and does not allow you to prepare at a sufficient level for the lesson.

Teachers also note that it is very difficult to study gymnastic terminology, emphasize the complexity and large amount of material, and if there is a break in the practice of its use, the terminology is forgotten and knowledge can be restored only provided that practical training and use of educational materials on this topic. Most teachers note that the level of possession of gymnastic terminology is influenced by the basic knowledge that they received while still in physical education classes, especially in junior and high school. If the teacher in the classroom professionally used gymnastic terminology and required his knowledge from the students, then during the years of studying at school she was very memorable, and in the further professional activity acquired the important value and significantly contributed to the improvement of the level of personal professional competence. Also a significant reason for neglect of gymnastic terminology teachers is low wages. Also, the analysis of the survey showed that the level of possession of gymnastic terminology is influenced by sports specialization of the teacher. It was found that representatives of such sports as martial arts, boxing, sports games, tourism assess their level of possession of gymnastic terminology as medium and low. Representatives of gymnastic sports traditionally rate their level as average and high. Pedagogical observations confirmed that teachers who have a specialization related to gymnastic sports really have sufficient knowledge of terminology and effectively apply it in physical education classes, and teachers - representatives of «non-hymen» sports own it at a much lower level.

An important reason for the lack of knowledge of sports (in particular, gymnastic) terminology, most teachers (58 of 87) call the fact that the actual curriculum for physical education, namely, state requirements for the level of general education of students does not provide for their knowledge of the terms, in particular, gymnastic exercises, which in turn gives the teacher the opportunity not to pay attention to terminology in general, despite the fact that they all recognize the need for its application.

Despite the fact that the program is constantly updated, it is supplemented by a large number of modern requirements,

tasks and recommendations, and new modules are constantly added to it, the level of physical education lessons is getting worse every year. The practical material of the program has not been revised for a very long time and at present a lot of exercises and tests do not correspond to the level of preparedness and health indicators of students. About the questions of terminology in the program does not even go. Unfortunately, in it the terminological errors occur.

Careful analysis of the updated curriculum on physical culture for general education schools (for grades 5–9) [17] found that it included new, unconventional and unusual for schoolchildren and teachers training modules such as «corfbal», «cheerleading», «Military sports games» and others. Even in them, in the chapter «theoretical information» we are not talking about the terminology of the sport. In the explanatory note of the updated program, the specified contribution of the subject «physical culture» to the formation of key competencies of students. One of them is «communication between the state (and native in case of difference) languages», which is a component of the formation of students' ability to «correctly use the terminological apparatus, communicate in various situations during physical education and sports, communicate through conflicts, culture and sport by language means. At the same time, the training resources recommended by the updated program include the study of Ukrainian sports terminology [17]. But the analysis of the program material in the training modules has revealed that there is practically no terminology in them, and it is practically impossible to form the necessary competence, since the content of the educational material of all modules does not provide for the study of terms, in particular, Gorodki, Fencing and Sport orienteering, where in the known component it is offered to know the basics of the terminology of these sports. The module «Gymnastics», applied in the main school, is called up, where the theoretical information was included in the section «The content of the educational material» without questions from the gymnastic terminology. In practical material, which includes special physical training, exercises on gymnastics instruments, acrobatics exercises and others, the gymnastic terminology of the language also does not go, although it is impossible to carry out these exercises effectively without knowledge of special terms. At the same time, the section «Expected results of educational and cognitive activity of students» is focused on qualitative assimilation of knowledge, skills and skills of the presented material [17]. Therefore, without the revision of the school curriculum on physical culture, the main document that is always used by both an experienced and a novice teacher, it is impossible to change the existing situation.

Conclusions

Based on our research, it was established that knowledge and skilful use of terms testifies to the level of terminological competence of the teacher of physical culture. Despite the important role of the use of terminology in physical education lessons, its component in the lesson decreases every

year, which is why the elimination of the gymnastics module largely contributes to it. The level of possession of gymnastic terminology for each specialist is individual and very often requires an increase. Observing the terminological competence of teachers in physical education classes revealed some significant terminological mistakes in the presentation of the training material. There was revealed a positive trend in the practice of attracting students to self-assembly and conducting complexes of general development exercises using gymnastic terminology. A number of reasons were identified that, in our opinion, significantly affect the level of terminological competence of teachers and are reflected in the quality of professional activities in general. The results of pedagogical observations revealed that teachers, representatives of sports and rhythmic gymnastics, acrobatics better know gymnastic terminology and apply it professionally enough in physical education classes than teachers specializing in single combats, boxing and sports games.

Thus, the results of the whole complex of studies carried out confirm the conclusions of many specialists that, despite the rather long time of application of gymnastic terminology in physical education, the quality of its use is not improving today, but, on the contrary, it is deteriorating noticeably [9–11; 14]. The conclusions of I. B. Grinchenko [3], E. S. Vilchkovsky [2], S. A. Mekhonoshin [18], M. M. Zheleznyi and V. V. Chernyakova [27], V. I. Malets [16], N. M. Kovalchuk and V. I. Sanyuk [9] and other scientists on the existence of problems related to the level of readiness of physical education teachers for the implementation of professional activities. The results of our research supplement the data of scientific works of N. M. Kovalchuk and V. I. Sanyuk concerning the insufficient level of terminological competence in teachers of physical culture and confirm the conclusions of these specialists about the necessity of knowledge of gymnastic terminology not only by teachers but also by pupils as part of professional readiness teachers of physical education [9–11; 13]. Confirmed data A. Kh. Deineko on increasing the motivation of students to physical education lessons, provided they are involved in self-assembly and conducting complexes of general development exercises for evaluation and competitions for the best complex [4; 6; 7]. But quantitative data on the specifics of teachers' use of gymnastic terminology in the lessons of physical culture and the level of possession of it in the work of specialists are not presented. Also, for the first time, the reasons that led to the current decline in the role of gymnastic terminology in physical education lessons are considered; identified factors are essential, necessary for lighting and require their elimination.

Prospects for further research. In subsequent studies it is planned to find out the level of knowledge of sports terminology by coaches in various sports.

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